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New concepts for solid oxide cells manufacturing: The use of 3D printing technologies

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Abstract

Manufacturing processes and final shapes of solid oxide cells (SOC) are, nowadays, constrained by ceramic fabrication technologies capable of shaping used materials with reasonable time and costs (tape casting and screen printing). The use of additive manufacturing technologies and its free-forming design for SOC manufacturing overcomes the commented limitations. Performance, durability and reliability are shown to be improved due to the enhancement of the active area and the addition of new geometrical features on SOC. For this purpose, electrolyte supported cells based on structured electrolytes were produced by stereo-lithography (SLA) 3D printing of 8YSZ. This pieces have demonstrated to present an improvement of the performance directly proportional to the increase on the active area induced by their structuration. A further implementation of this technology is the hybridization of SLA with a robocasting system as a multimaterial hybrid printer system to produce a one-step printed monolithic SOFC stack. This approach reduces the manufacturing steps and the waste material while avoiding the manual steps and multiple sintering steps of the conventional process. Complete SOFC fully printed by SLA+Robocasting hybrid printing are here presented. Challenges and results of the processing and co-sintering are discussed.

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Introduction

The interest of renewable energies have been increased as the alternative to overcome the depletion of fossil fuels and the reduction of greenhouse gases emissions in a new energy scenario. This alternative energy sources presents their main drawback in the discontinuity of energy production. To overcome this problem different solutions based on energy storage have been proposed such as batteries that are leading the recent research. However, fuel cells are also widely developed and play an important role as one of the most perspective approaches due to the capability to directly convert chemical energy stored in the hydrogen bonds into electrical power with a high efficiency under continuous operation.

Implementation of fuel cells based devices into the energetic grid provides an opportunity to save excess of renewable energy in hydrogen form and restoring this electricity during high demanding hours due to the reversibility of the devices. [1] In contrast to other types of fuel cells, SOFCs present the higher efficiency and the possibility of working not only with hydrogen, but with a wider range of fuels. [2-3]

Due to the ceramic nature of the materials that form the electrolyte, the devices based on SOC technology are mostly constraint into two shapes: tubular and flat devices, [4] derived from manufacturing technologies like tape casting, screen printing, extrusion and infiltration. Other techniques are precluded because of to the material's stiffness which makes them hard to machine with high cost and tool consumption. Those aspects precluded are limiting the design of the electrolyte and consequently the improvements related to a potential structuration of the surface. Some efforts to increase the performance of these devices through an increase of their surface area were made by *Cebollero et al.* [5-6] through micro-laser machining of the surface. In this sense, a possible solution was proposed by *Ruiz-Morales et al.* [7] suggesting the use of additive manufacturing for energy applications. In particular, they explored works in the field of SOFCs and batteries. At the time of the publication, the studies on 3D printing of SOFCs were focused on the inkjet and aerosol jet printing of electrolyte and cathode layers. According to previous works [8-18] the use of 3D printing technologies was limited to the deposition of a functional layer on top of a support layer, usually the anode or the electrolyte. Additive manufacturing techniques offer the possibility of realize free-design shapes, exploring solution forbidden by other production techniques. To achieve the maximum output of the device, simulation of different electrolyte geometries with different aspect ratio have been performed in the last years and the 3D printing has been proposed to obtain these untraditional structures. [19-20] Due to the intrinsic features of additive manufacturing techniques some studies have been devoted to increase the output of the device increasing the area of the electrolyte, which plays the role of supporting layer, and consequentially increasing the surface of the entire device. [21-24]

1. Scientific Approach

The work here presented is dedicated to prove the advantage and capability of the use of 3D printing technologies to the SOCs manufacturing and how the performance of these devices may be implemented thanks to the freedom of design achievable by these technologies.

The significant advantage of the additive manufacturing is the high automation of the process, compared with others techniques. A study from *Weimar et al.* shows how the production of a commercial stacks requires more than a hundred steps [25], the *Cell3Ditor European project*, [26-27] proposed the use of 3D printing to manufacture a stack in a single production and a single sintering step. In this frame, a stereo-lithography system has been equipped with a robocasting one, with four nozzles to enable the production of

pieces made of five different materials at the same time. Preliminary results on this implementation in a fuel cell are here presented.

2. Experiments

Electrolytes are printed out from a commercial slurry of 8mol%YSZ (3DMix, France), which is made of ceramic particles and organic compounds (monomer and photo initiator), which appear as a high viscosity paste [28]. The slurry is fed into a commercial ceramic 3D printer (3DCERAM, France)[29-30], a piston supply the necessary amount of the paste onto the building surface after which a double doctor blade system spreads the paste over the printing platform to get a thin and homogenous layer of 25 μm . A diode UV laser focused at the building surface reproduces the pattern designed by CAD (Computer assisted Design) software. Under UV exposure, the polymerization process takes place and the paste is solidified according to the desired shape. After each stage, the platform moves down and the process is repeated; since the curing depth of the laser is higher than the thickness of the layer deposited by tape casting, each slice is attached to the previous, generating a three dimensional structure (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Scheme of stereo-lithography system.

Pursuing the improve of the performance changing the area with structuration of the electrolyte, a wave profile (Figure 2.b) extruded in a direction was produced with the technique described here, allowing an increase of active area of 57% compared with a flat design of the same external dimensions, used as comparison as typical geometry of traditional manufacturing as tape casting and screen printing (Figure 2.a).

At the end of the printing process, it is necessary to collect the uncured paste to be re-used in further printing, before fire the parts at high temperature in order to remove the organic compounds and sintering the ceramic part, to get the final mechanical properties of the pieces.

In order to reduce the ohmic losses of the final produced cells [31] electrolytes are printed as membranes (thickness of 300 μm), a thick ring (3mm) is added to the structure to increase its mechanical integrity and help with its handling [21,23], moreover, the design of this ring has been adapted for installation and sealing inside the testing station. The electrolytes have been sintered at 1300°C for 3 hours to ensure fully densification.

The freedom of design, producing a wave profile, changing the external dimensions and improving the structural structures to improve the assembly of the pieces, are features proving the advantage of additive manufacturing technologies, these same solutions would be forbidden by traditional manufacturing or obtained at high cost, time and consumption of the tools.

Figure 2: CAD designs used in this work, a) flat design, b) corrugated design, as well called wave..

Commercial inks are used for the electrodes: NiO-YSZ (Fuelcellmaterials, USA) as fuel electrode and LSM-YSZ (Fuelcellmaterials, USA) as oxygen electrode, attachment optimization is not reported here and can be found previous publications of the same authors. [23]

Fully printed cells were manufactured with the same printer hybridized with a robocasting system. This consists on a robotic arm, equipped with four syringes, valves and needles integrated to allow the printing of five materials at the same time. In this work SLA system was used to produce the electrolyte, which gives the mechanical support of the electrodes produced by robocasting. State-of-the-art materials for electrolyte supported cells were used, 8YSZ for the electrolyte, LSM-YSZ for the air electrode and NiO-YSZ for the fuel one. After the removal of the organic compounds, through a debinding process, the cells were co-sintered at 1250°C for two hours.

All the cells based on the printed electrolytes have been tested in co-electrolysis and fuel cell mode. The electrochemical characterizations are performed in a commercial ProboStat™ (NorECs AS, Norway), the sample holder of which is placed inside a high temperature tubular furnace, tests were run at 850°-900°C. Gold meshes and inks were employed as current collector for both electrodes. Ceramabond™ (Aremco, USA) sealant paste was applied to ensure gas tightness between the anodic and the cathodic chambers. The electrochemical performance is evaluated through I-V curves performed by a multimeter (Parstat 2273, PAR, USA), voltage is measured at each current step up to a maximum potential of 0,6V in fuel cell mode and 1,4V in co-electrolysis mode to limit degradation. The polarization curves are extrapolated up to 0,4V to show the maximum power output. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is carried out using a potentiostat/galvanostat frequency response analyzer (Parstat 2273, PAR, USA) in the frequency range of 100 kHz down to 100 mHz and an amplitude of 50 mV under OCV and operative conditions, at 0,7V for SOFC mode and 1,3V for co-SOEC mode, conditions in which the resistive behavior is linear. During fuel cell mode measurements, the anodic side was fed with 22,2ml/min·cm² of hydrogen, and the cathodic one with synthetic air at 55ml/min·cm². In co-electrolysis mode the fuel electrode was fed with a mixture of 11,6 mg/min·cm² of water, 5,52 ml/min·cm² of carbon dioxide and 2,22 ml/min·cm² of hydrogen while the oxygen electrode was supplied with 45 ml/min·cm² of synthetic air. The fully printed cells have been tested only in SOFC mode, the same preparation and test conditions have been applied.

Microstructural characterization is performed using an AURIGA Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) from ZEISS (Germany), equipped with a Schottky gun and an Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analyser (SEM-EDX) to measure the composition of the samples.

3. Results

Cells based on electrolytes produced by stereo-lithography

Stereo-lithography has been proved to be a suitable way to manufacture gas-tight electrolytes, showing properties comparable with the ones produced by traditional manufacturing. The final electrolytes show low and not-interconnected porosity, as it can be seen in Figure 3, where small pores are present, but the total density is over 97% of the theoretical value. The suitable density has been proved further on by electrochemical characterization, showing proper OCV values, above 1.05V. Gas tightness is critical issue, since pinholes and other defects could affect the performance of the cell

Figure 3: SEM micrograph of the printed electrolyte after sintering at 1350°C.

Figure 2: Post-mortem analysis of the tested cells, a) planar cell, b) wave cell. The active layers are reported.

Figure 4 presents the overall structure of the electrolytes produced as it has been previously described, showing proper thickness of the electrodes and confirming the reproduction of the CAD designs. It is possible to observe a proper porosity of the electrodes, allowing the diffusion of gases, and their good adhesion to the electrolyte.

As first step of the electrochemical characterization, the Open Circuit Voltage is measured and recorded over time during the *in situ* reduction of the fuel electrode, the values obtained are used to follow the reduction process and to confirm the gas-tightness of the cell and the sealing. Figure 5 shows the behavior of the voltage over time, the steps observed are related with the increase of the hydrogen against the argon in the fuel

electrode chamber, the final value of the OCV, before the measurement was stabilized at 1.14 V, confirming the gas-tightness of the electrolyte and of the applied sealing.

Figure 3: OCV over time at 850°C during the reduction until before the measurement

The I-V polarization curves performed on fuel cell mode shown an important improvement due to the corrugation of the electrolyte (Figure 6.a). The maximum output power is improved from 287 mW/cm² to 455 mW/cm², corresponding the increase on the active area. Looking into detail of the Nyquist plots obtained by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (Figure 6.b), it is highlighted how the decreasing of the resistance is present, but not limited, to the serial resistance, which collects all the ohmic contributions, cables, electrolytes, etc., and to the polarisation resistance. In particular, the decrease ascribed to the reduce in the serial resistance, decreasing from 0.38 Ω·cm² to 0.32 Ω·cm², contribute for the 13% to the overall decrease in ASR, from 1.14 Ω·cm² to 0.68 Ω·cm², while the bigger contribution, ca. 87% is ascribed to the polarization resistance, which decrease from 0.75 Ω·cm² to 0.36 Ω·cm².

Figure 6: Electrochemical characterization of the cells based on printed electrolytes, carried out in SOFC mode at 900°C. a) IV curves of planar and wave cells, b) Nyquist plot of the EIS at 0.7 V.

The cells have been tested in co-SOEC mode, to prove their suitability to be used to reduce CO₂. The improvement correlated with the area is maintained, but less relevant than the observed in SOFC mode, in this case the performance is evaluated comparing the injected current at 1.3V. The injected current is 432 mA/cm² for the planar, while for the corrugated one, the value increase up to 567 mA/cm², corresponding to an increase of 31%, lower than the improve of 57% of the area. This difference can be ascribed to water feeding or diffusion issues. The same problem was detected in the recording of the EIS, the instability of the measurement does not allow a good resolution of the arcs. In this case, only the serial resistance has been considered, showing a decrease of 0.128 Ω·cm²,

which cannot be the only contribution to the increase in the performance, corresponding only to a 25% reduction in resistance.

Figure 7: Electrochemical characterization of the cells based on printed electrolytes, carried out in co-SOEC mode at 900°C. a) IV curves of planar and wave cells, b) Nyquist plot of the EIS at OCV.

Hybrid cell

Another approach based on the 3D printing of SOFC devices is to hybrid printing (SLA+Robocasting) of complete cells. Here the preliminary results are presented for the single step manufacturing, in which all the components were produced by additive manufacturing techniques, robocasting for the electrodes and stereo-lithography for the electrolyte, which plays the role of support layer. The printed cell was co-sintered at 1250°C, after the removal of the organics by a debinding thermal treatment.

Series of Figure 8 shows the microstructure of the different components of the cells after the co-sintering, respectively, the air electrode, the electrolyte and the fuel electrode. The LSM-YSZ electrode shows a non-optimized densification, open to further development, it is important to notice that although the lower sintering temperature compared with the samples presented before (Figure 3), the electrolyte appears dense, with small and not connected porosity. The NiO-YSZ electrode presents higher porosity compared to the LSM-YSZ, due to the higher sintering temperature of this material.

Figure 8: SEM analysis of the post-mortem: a) air electrode, b) electrolyte, c) fuel electrode of the fully printed cell, co-sintered at 1250°C for 2 hours.

Figure 9 reports the electrochemical characterization in fuel mode, the OCV is lower than the value obtained on the cells reported before, this behaviour is ascribed to pinholes and cracks in the electrolyte generated by the thermal stress during the sintering.

The maximum output power at 900°C is 80 mW/cm², this result is very promising, since the resistance is in accordance with the thickness of the cell. Higher output power is expected optimizing the porosity of the electrodes and improving the initial OCV of the cell.

Figure 9: Potentiostatic curves of the fully printed and co-sintered cell at 850°C and 900°C.

4. Conclusion

In this work we explored the capability of the 3D printing in the Solid Oxide Cells scenario, stereo-lithography has been applied to improve the performance of the devices accordingly to the increase of the area. The performance improves of 58% in SOFC mode and of 31% upfront an increase of the area of the 57%.

Preliminary results on a fully printed and co-sintered cell are here reported, although the performance are lower compared with the cells based on the printed electrolytes, a promising possibility in the production of fuel cell has been proved.

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